

Ressentiment, Victimhood, and Revanchism

Unpacking Erdoğan's Populist Mastery

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Abstract: *Introduction:* This article examines the emotional foundations of Recep Tayyip Erdoğan's populism through social and political psychology, focusing on resentment as a collective emotion that transforms historical humiliation into moralized pride and political mobilization. *Method:* Using critical discourse analysis of Erdoğan's speeches between 2012 and 2018, including the National Culture Forum (3 March 2017) and Civilizational Forum (21 October 2017), the study analyzes texts emphasizing civilization, culture, and faith through interpretative-phenomenological coding informed by theories of collective emotions, moral regulation, and identity repair. *Results:* Findings show that resentment functions as both an emotional mechanism and a political resource, converting collective victimhood into moral triumph and legitimizing authoritarian consolidation and a neo-Ottomanist revival, demonstrating how Erdoğan's populism operates as an affective regime binding followers through shared emotions of loss, pride, and revenge.

Keywords: *resentiment*, victimhood, Islamism, laicism, neo-Ottomanism, revanchism

Introduction

As a political symbol in his own right, Recep Tayyip Erdoğan has adeptly embodied and mobilized a wide spectrum of emotions throughout his political trajectory. Rooted in a narrative of victimization enriched with potent historical allusions, he has reframed this narrative into one of triumph, grandeur, and resurgence. Central to this transformation is the ethos of neo-Ottomanism, which draws its emotional force from a collective sense of *resentiment* embedded within a discourse of victimhood. This narrative reflects not only Erdoğan's personal history but also the collective memory of the Islamic conservative tradition – a tradition profoundly shaped by a legacy of perceived historical injustices, broken dignity, humiliation, and exclusion. Psychologically, this dynamic exemplifies how *collective emotions* such as resentment, *resentiment*, pride, and perceived injustice become mobilized in the service of *collective identity restoration* (Smith, 1993; Bar-Tal et al., 2009; Sullivan & Landau, 2020). The enduring wound of humiliation that followed the disintegration of the Ottoman Empire functions as a form of *cultural trauma*, deeply imprinting collective memory and shaping the emotional grammar through which the past and present are interpreted.

In Turkey's modernization process, the hierarchical structure of centre-periphery relations has perpetuated uneven participation and deep-seated affective inequalities. Following Eisenstadt's (1981) argument that elites

acted as centres of modernization, the Kemalist governments, particularly under the Republican People's Party (CHP), pursued what Giddens (1994) termed "simple modernization" – a top-down approach to homogenize the nation. This produced a secular, bureaucratic elite that monopolized symbolic and material capital, relegating the traditional working classes and religiously conservative groups to a peripheral status. Over time, this structural marginalization nurtured *collective resentment* – a sustained emotional orientation of envy, humiliation, and moral superiority toward the "centre." In psychological terms, *resentiment* can be understood as a *chronic affective state* arising when aggression cannot be directly expressed, leading to moral reevaluation and displacement (Scheler, 1915/2010; TenHouten, 2007). Such emotions, once politicized, fuel narratives of *collective victimhood* and *moral revanchism* (Noor et al., 2012; Bar-Tal & Halperin, 2011).

The article is structured in five parts. The first outlines the methodological design of the study, detailing the qualitative and interpretive strategies used to analyze Erdoğan's discourse. The second develops the theoretical framework, elaborating the concept of *resentiment* through Nietzsche and Scheler to clarify its emotional, moral, and psychological dynamics. The third section examines Erdoğan's charismatic and populist leadership style, showing how he activates and governs through the *resentiment* of his supporters. The fourth analyzes his neo-Ottomanist and Islamist rhetoric as mechanisms for constructing an affective regime that positions followers in civilizational opposition

to the West. The final section explores how his broader civilizational narrative facilitates the internalization of moralized pride and historical continuity, consolidating a durable emotional and political bond between leader and constituency.

Methodology and Research Design

This article employs a qualitative design that combines critical discourse analysis (CDA) and Foucauldian discourse analysis (FDA), drawing on political psychology and the psychology of emotions to examine the emotional architecture of Erdoğan's populism. Focusing on how his rhetoric evokes and regulates collective emotions – such as humiliation, pride, resentment, and loyalty – it analyzes how these affective dynamics contribute to the construction of a threatened yet morally superior national self. CDA provides the foundation for exploring the ideological and power-laden dimensions of his language, informed by Fairclough's (1995, 2003) and van Dijk's (1998) work on discourse, ideology, and elite dominance, as well as Wodak and Meyer's (2016) and Reisigl and Wodak's (2001) insights into historical narrative and collective memory. Complementing this, FDA foregrounds the formation of subjectivities, moral regulation, and affective regimes, drawing on Foucault's (1972, 1978, 1980) conceptualization of discourse as a system of knowledge and power and its methodological extensions (Kendall & Wickham, 1999; Willig, 2013). Integrating CDA and FDA thus enables a multi-level analysis of Erdoğan's discourse as both an instrument of ideological mobilization and a mechanism through which emotional subjects are positioned and governed.

The data corpus for this study consists of a purposive selection of Erdoğan's political speeches delivered between 2012 and 2018, a period marked by the intensification of civilizational rhetoric, political polarization, and the consolidation of a nationalist-Islamist state discourse and his authoritarian power. This study involved secondary analysis of publicly available political speeches and did not involve direct data collection from human participants. The period between 2012 and 2018 represents a crucial phase in the affective reconfiguration of Turkish politics, in which victimhood was transformed into a discourse of

moral triumph and civilizational renewal. The primary texts analyzed include Erdoğan's speeches at the Turkish-Arab Tourism Summit in Bursa (22 April 2012),¹ The National Culture Forum in Istanbul (3 March 2017),² The Civilizational Forum at Ibn Khaldun University (21 October 2017),³ The opening of the new Istanbul airport on the Republic Day (29 October 2018),⁴ and several key campaign speeches available through the Presidency of the Republic of Turkey archives and verified media transcripts. Texts were selected based on their explicit reference to civilization (*medeniyet*), culture, faith, perceived historical injustices, broken dignity, humiliation, pride, revenge, and moral renewal – core signifiers in Erdoğan's populist and neo-Ottomanist discourse.

The final corpus was derived from an initial collection of more than thirty speeches from the same period. From this larger pool, texts were retained only when emotional themes clearly recurred across multiple contexts and venues, allowing findings to emerge inductively from patterned discursive regularities rather than isolated quotations. These speeches were chosen not only for their thematic relevance but also for their prominence within Turkey's mediated public sphere, where they play a central role in shaping emotional climates and political imaginaries in ways consistent with CDA's focus on ideological reproduction. All speeches were collected from official state communication outlets and mainstream media. To preserve semantic nuance, they were analyzed in Turkish before selected excerpts were translated into English for interpretation.

The analysis proceeded through an iterative, interpretive engagement with the texts, beginning with repeated, immersive readings to contextualize Erdoğan's rhetorical style, affective cues, and the sociopolitical conditions surrounding each speech – an approach consistent with the FDA's emphasis on situating discourse within broader power formations (Foucault, 1980). Based on this grounding, a blended coding strategy was developed that integrated the textual and argumentative tools of CDA (Fairclough, 2003; Wodak & Meyer, 2016) with FDA's focus on subject positions, moral injunctions, and emotional governance (Willig, 2013). Initial open codes, such as *wound*, *moral superiority*, and *civilizational mission*, were refined into axial categories, including humiliation-pride conversion and moralized victimhood, which ultimately

¹ Erdoğan's Turkish-Arab Tourism Summit Speech, <https://www.dunya.com/gundem/sirtimizi-dogu039ya-guney039e-donmeyiz-haberi-172151>, accessed on 22 November 2025.

² Erdoğan's Third National Culture Forum Speech <https://basin.ktb.gov.tr/TR-175032/3-milli-kultur-surasi-basladi.html>, accessed on 22 November 2025.

³ For Erdoğan's Civilizational Forum Speech (21 October 2017), see <https://www.fikriyat.com/kultur-sanat/2017/10/21/medeniyetler-surasi-basladi>, accessed on 22 November 2025.

⁴ Erdoğan's Istanbul Airport Opening Speech, <https://www.tccb.gov.tr/en/speeches-statements/558/99431/president-erdogan-s-message-on-29-october-republic-day>, accessed on 22 November 2025.

informed higher-order theoretical constructs, including resentment, identity repair, and revanchism. For example, repeated references to “historical injustices” and “broken dignity” were coded within a broader resentment frame that consolidated into the affective mechanism of *ressentiment*. Guided by sensitizing concepts from affect theory (Ahmed, 2004; Wetherell, 2012), the process grouped textual segments into thematic clusters tracing emotional trajectories such as the transformation of humiliation into pride, victimhood into moral superiority, and grievance into political revenge.

Interpretation then moved toward a synthetic reading of the themes, with CDA revealing how Erdoğan’s discourse legitimizes political strategies, constructs antagonistic binaries, and reframes historical humiliation as collective empowerment, following Fairclough (1995) and van Dijk (1998), while FDA illuminated how these discourses constitute emotionally defined subjects through moral norms, affective prescriptions, and civilizational narratives (Foucault, 1978; Kendall & Wickham, 1999). Together, these approaches positioned resentment not simply as an emotional state but as a discursive-political technology that produces compliant subjects and justifies revanchist ambitions. Analytic rigor was ensured through iterative cross-checking of codes, detailed memoing of interpretative decisions, and thick description (Willig, 2013). Reflexive awareness also shaped the process: the researcher’s prior work on Turkish politics and the AKP (Kaya, 2013, 2015, 2021) informed analytic sensitivities while ongoing reflexive memoing helped mitigate bias and contextualize culturally specific cues. As the study relied exclusively on publicly available speeches, formal ethical approval was not required, though ethical reflexivity guided the interpretation of emotionally charged and exclusionary state narratives.

By integrating CDA’s focus on ideology with FDA’s attention to subject formation and regimes of truth, the methodological design situates Erdoğan’s rhetoric within a broader psychosocial framework of identity threat, collective trauma, and moral regulation. This combined approach allows themes to emerge inductively from patterned discursive regularities, enabling neo-Ottomanism to be analyzed not only as a political project but as an *affective regime* through which collective resentment becomes a source of legitimacy, solidarity, and domination. Empirically, the analysis asks how Erdoğan’s rhetoric evokes and regulates emotions such as humiliation, pride, and resentment; how these affective dynamics shape a threatened yet morally elevated national self; and how resentment functions both as an emotional mechanism and a political resource sustaining populist identification. Addressing these questions demonstrates how collective emotional orientations mediate between historical grievance and political mobilization,

showing that resentment operates as a psychosocial mechanism of identity repair that links collective memory to political discourse under conditions of perceived injustice and broken dignity.

Ressentiment as an Emotional Mechanism: Friedrich Nietzsche and Max Scheler

Amid growing concern about the emotional volatility of democratic life under neoliberalism, the study of politics increasingly recognizes the affective currents shaping civic behavior and identity. As Flinders (2020) notes, emotions are intrinsic to modern citizenship rather than deviations from rational politics. Within this context, the Nietzschean concept of *ressentiment* has re-emerged as a powerful lens for understanding political disaffection, populism, and grievance-based identity formation. Derived from the Latin *resentire* – “to feel again” – *ressentiment* differs from ordinary resentment: it is a repetitive, self-perpetuating emotional state arising from perceived injustice, humiliation, or exclusion that cannot be directly acted upon (Ure, 2015). Nietzsche (1872/1967) describes it as a psychological mechanism through which the powerless transform impotence into moral superiority, converting injury into virtue and suffering into moral worth. In this sense, *ressentiment* is not a fleeting feeling but an affective structure of moral inversion – a “poisoned memory” that reshapes values and identities.

In Nietzsche’s (1872/1967) *Genealogy of Morals*, *ressentiment* originates in the “slave revolt in morality,” when the powerless invent a new moral code by redefining “good” as humility, meekness, and piety, and “evil” as the strength and vitality of the noble classes. This reversal constitutes, for Nietzsche, the psychological foundation of Christian morality, with its elevation of submissive virtues and its moral condemnation of the strong. *Ressentiment* therefore requires an external antagonist – an imagined oppressor – against whom self-worth is continually measured. Nietzsche’s (1872/1967: 127–128) observation that those consumed by *ressentiment* “tear open their oldest wounds and bleed from long-healed scars” captures its cyclical, self-poisoning nature. Unlike ordinary resentment, which may seek justice or repair, *ressentiment* is reactive, self-referential, and endlessly renewed through moral denunciation.

Psychologically, *ressentiment* functions as a collective emotional mechanism through which individuals unable to express anger outwardly internalize and moralize their grievances (Capelos & Demertzis, 2022). It represents a blocked affective circuit: desires for recognition or revenge

cannot be fulfilled, so they crystallize into chronic emotional orientations (TenHouten, 2007). This makes *ressentiment* highly politicizable, providing fertile ground for populist and authoritarian mobilization. Nietzsche's analysis remains salient because it anticipates the emotional logic of contemporary politics. Modern populisms, be it nationalist, religious, or identity-based, similarly frame constituencies as moral victims oppressed by elites or outsiders and justify revenge in the name of justice. Leaders like Recep Tayyip Erdoğan exemplify this dynamic: their rhetoric redefines exclusion as authenticity and humiliation as moral elevation. Through what Bar-Tal and Halperin (2011) call collective emotion regulation, *ressentiment* becomes a cohesive force of belonging.

While Nietzsche located *ressentiment* in Western Christian morality, Scheler (1915/2010) offered a more sociological and psychological reinterpretation. Scheler agreed that *ressentiment* involves envy, hostility, and moralizing hatred, but situated its origins in the structural inequalities of modern democratic societies. For him, it was less a product of slave morality than a symptom of modernity's unfulfilled promises – particularly the unrealized ideals of liberty, equality, and fraternity (Fantini et al., 2013). He argued that sustained feelings of impotence and envy, when repressed and unexpressed, harden into stable moral emotions. As Scheler (1915/2010, 9–14) notes, “envy turns to hatred when the desired good becomes unattainable,” and this hatred becomes self-sustaining once moralized.

Scheler rejected Nietzsche's link between *ressentiment* and Christianity, locating it instead in capitalist competition, class stratification, and unequal access to education and prestige (Kaya et al., 2023; Minkinen, 2007). The emotional repression fostered by modern hierarchies produces a tension between aspiration and powerlessness; when this tension cannot be resolved through action, it manifests as moralized hostility and reevaluation of social values. Contemporary social psychology echoes these insights: chronic disadvantage often leads groups to construct narratives of moral superiority and suffering to preserve self-esteem (Bar-Tal et al., 2009; Branscombe et al., 1999; Noor et al., 2012). *Ressentiment*, from this perspective, functions as an identity strategy that restores dignity through moral comparison when material equality is unattainable.

Populist movements capitalize on this affective structure by offering “meaning systems” that restore ontological security in times of uncertainty (Sullivan & Landau, 2020). *Ressentiment* supplies such meaning by transforming diffuse frustration into a coherent moral narrative and framing status decline as a collective mission. In Erdoğan's Turkey, for instance, *ressentiment* fuses memories of humiliation, stemming from secular exclusion and perceived Western domination, into a civilizational project of Islamist revival. Through emotionally charged narratives of betrayal

and resurrection, Erdoğan converts *ressentiment* into political affect: a shared sense of being wronged yet chosen.

Scheler (1915/2010) identified two defining features of *ressentiment*: its persistence and its hostility. It accumulates suppressed anger, envy, and revenge until they become enduring emotional dispositions, directing moral hostility toward entire categories such as elites, secularists, or Western powers. Contemporary political psychology affirms this pattern: *ressentiment* differs from prosocial anger because it is passive, nostalgic, and moralizing rather than action-oriented (Capelos & Demertzis, 2022). It sustains cycles of victimhood and nostalgia, making individuals receptive to populist promises of symbolic revenge. Erdoğan's discourse, depicting laicist-secular elites as oppressors of pious Muslims, exemplifies this process: it transforms humiliation into pride and exclusion into destiny. This emotional logic helps explain why *ressentiment* can persist even among the powerful. As Marañón (1956) observed in his study of Emperor Tiberius, feelings of inferiority and vengeance may endure despite success, fueling cruelty as displaced retaliation. Modern populist leaders similarly channel collective *ressentiment* into symbolic or actual retribution. Erdoğan's leadership embodies this “revenge of the peripheral,” where personal and collective *ressentiment* converge to produce moralized victimhood and authority.

Distinguishing *ressentiment* from ordinary resentment clarifies its psychological implications. Resentment, as Adam Smith (1759) and later sociologists like Meltzer and Musolf (2002) argue, can be a moral protest that seeks justice; it is transient and repair-oriented. *Ressentiment*, by contrast, is enduring, self-reinforcing, and identity-forming: it magnifies humiliation, moralizes envy, and anchors belonging in grievance (Demertzis, 2020; Salmela & Capelos, 2021). Under neoliberal conditions of inequality and cultural dislocation, *ressentiment* becomes politically exploitable. As Brown (2018) suggests, it underpins the nihilistic tendencies of contemporary populism, where truth dissolves into affective narratives. Leaders skilled in emotional reframing, such as Erdoğan, convert diffuse frustration into political loyalty through narratives of grievance, redemption, and divine justice. In this sense, *ressentiment* becomes political capital – an emotion of the masses reinterpreted as a civilizational mission of the nation.

The collective emotions generated and mobilized among AKP supporters are often characterized by a potent mix of positive, ingroup bonding emotions and negative, outgroup-directed emotions. The emotional landscape of Erdoğan's supporters is deeply intertwined with *ressentiment*, understood as a moralized form of grievance and victimhood that transforms perceived humiliation into a source of collective meaning (Tokdoğan, 2024). Their emotional loyalty and performative love for the leader operate

not merely as personal sentiments but as politically charged affects that anchor individuals within a broader narrative of redemption against hostile elites and foreign conspirators (Kaya, 2019). In this sense, *ressentiment* is sustained by a fusion of individual emotions, such as affection, anger, or pride, with collective feelings that are repeatedly cultivated in rallies, partisan media, and public ceremonies (Bozoğlu, 2019). The collective anger and sense of victimhood directed at “internal and external enemies” intensify this dynamic by providing a shared interpretive frame through which personal frustrations are refracted into a larger struggle for national dignity. At the same time, collective pride, especially the techno-nationalist enthusiasm displayed during Technofests and celebrations of Turkey’s indigenous technological achievements, such as domestically built jets, drones, other military hardware, and the electric vehicle brand Togg (Üngör, 2025), offers a counter-affect that transforms *ressentiment* into a sense of civilizational rejuvenation (Yilmaz and Morieson, 2023). This interplay highlights that the political potency of Erdoğan’s populism lies neither in individual emotions nor in collective ones alone, but in the feedback loop between them: personal affect is affirmed, amplified, and moralized through collective rituals, while collective emotions gain durability by being internalized as part of supporters’ everyday political subjectivity.

Hence, *ressentiment* is not merely an emotion of the weak but a psychological mechanism of *identity repair* under conditions of perceived inequality and humiliation. It transforms personal frustration into moral righteousness, private envy into collective civilizational mission, and loss into imagined revenge. Integrating Nietzsche’s philosophical critique with Scheler’s social psychology, and drawing on contemporary theories of *collective emotions* (Smith, 1993; Bar-Tal et al., 2009) and *threatened identity* (Branscombe et al., 1999), allows us to understand Erdoğan’s populism as more than political opportunism. It is an *emotional regime* organized around *ressentiment*: the affective glue that binds historical grievance, moral superiority, and nationalist redemption.

The Rise of Erdoğan: A Charismatic and Populist Leader from the Periphery

Scholars generally distinguish three main approaches to the study of populism. The first is the socioeconomic or “losers of modernization” approach, which explains populist support as a reaction to the dislocations of globalization and neoliberal restructuring, disproportionately affecting working-class groups and structural outsiders (Betz, 1994; Fenema, 2004; de Vries & Hoffmann, 2016). The second,

the ethnonationalist or antielitist approach, highlights how right-wing populism mobilizes myths of a homogeneous national past and resentment toward liberal elites who are accused of imposing multiculturalism and minority rights against the will of “ordinary people” (Rydgren, 2007). A third approach views populism as a political style or strategic repertoire, emphasizing the discursive techniques through which charismatic leaders construct “the people” and mobilize support (Moffitt, 2016). Many scholars use these approaches eclectically, noting their regional variation and their usefulness for analyzing contemporary cases shaped by strong leadership dynamics.

Recep Tayyip Erdoğan’s rise represents a paradigmatic case for such an eclectic lens, as his ascent draws simultaneously on socioeconomic grievances, cultural resentment, and a distinctive populist style. Emerging from the vacuum created by the 2001 economic crisis, Erdoğan and the newly founded AKP capitalized on widespread frustration and humiliation (Kaya, 2015). His imprisonment in 1998 elevated him as a symbol of pious victimhood for the conservative periphery – segments long feeling culturally marginalized and politically excluded by the secular-Kemalist establishment (Tuğal, 2009). Economic dislocation, antielite sentiment, and resentment among these groups provided fertile ground for Erdoğan to frame himself not just as a political leader but as an agent of moral vindication and collective redemption.

Erdoğan’s appeal rests on a carefully crafted dual image: both ordinary and extraordinary. He performs ordinariness through slang, emotional speeches, and culturally resonant gestures, such as walking through dusty neighborhoods in his *presto* jacket without a tie, signaling proximity to “the people” (Moffitt, 2016; Ostiguy, 2009). Simultaneously, he cultivates an aura of exceptionalism, reinforced by monikers like *Uzun Adam*, repeated references to wearing a “shroud,” and his self-presentation as a divinely guided leader (Çay, 2022; Kaya, 2019). This blending of familiarity and mythic charisma exemplifies the broader populist repertoire: leaders who embody both the people’s common experience and their uncommon salvation.

Crucially, Erdoğan’s populist style is powered by *ressentiment*, Islamism, and neo-Ottoman nostalgia – elements that recast political competition as a moral struggle between “the pure people” and domestic or foreign “enemies” (Mudde, 2007; Moffitt, 2016). His upbringing in Kasımpaşa, sermon-like speaking style, Sunni-inflected rhetoric, and outsider persona enable him to appear as the authentic representative of the conservative masses against the secular elite (Kaya, 2015). Long-standing grievances among devout Muslims, stemming from restrictions on religious education, bans on public religiosity such as the headscarf, suppression of Sufi orders, and unequal access to state power, produced a sense of collective humiliation that

deeply shaped political identity (Kaya, 2013; Kuru, 2009; Yavuz, 2009; Lord, 2018). These intersecting forms of marginalization generated a durable resentment within conservative communities.

The AKP institutionalized this resentment by delivering symbolic recognition and socioeconomic mobility. Expanding *imam-hatip* (clerical) education, lifting headscarf restrictions, and normalizing public religiosity signaled the political restoration of previously excluded groups (Gurses et al., 2024; Kaya, 2019; Lord, 2018). Erdoğan's rhetoric transformed past exclusion into moral pride: Ottoman and Islamic references, valorization of piety, and framing the conservative base as the authentic "people" recoded humiliation into a righteous collective identity (Tokdoğan, 2024). Survey evidence confirms this shift, showing persistent support for the AKP in peripheral, religiously conservative provinces and strong correlations between religiosity, regional identity, and political loyalty (Çay, 2022; Gundem, 2023; Gurses et al., 2024).

Erdoğan mobilizes *ressentiment* by narrating past humiliations, such as the headscarf ban, military tutelage, and secularist disdain, as collective wounds that only he can avenge. Neo-Ottoman nostalgia serves as an affective resource: invoking imperial grandeur compensates for perceived historical decline and supplies an alternative civilizational horizon, reinforced by Davutoğlu's (2001, 2011) foreign policy imaginaries. Islamism functions as both an ideological frame and a moral boundary marker, legitimizing Erdoğan's leadership as a sacred duty against "corrupt elites" and external conspirators. This fusion of emotion, memory, and religion illustrates the cultural axis of populism, in which myth, heritage, and identity legitimize personalized rule (Wodak, 2015; Taggart, 2000).

This populist style hardened as Erdoğan dismantled the broad coalition that initially enabled his rise, alliances with the EU, the U.S., liberals, anti-Kemalist actors, and the Gülen movement (Kaya, 2015). Following the 2007 presidential crisis and the weakening of military veto players, Erdoğan shifted from reformist pluralism to majoritarian, plebiscitary authoritarianism. Resentment was redirected toward former allies, recast as traitors or foreign agents. The Islamization of the media sphere, the commodification of Islam through "Brand Turkey," and the production of Gramscian "professional intellectuals" (Kaya, 2015) further consolidated this turn. Neo-Ottomanism, initially aligned with EU accession, became a justification for unilateral foreign policy after the Arab Spring (Park, 2018; Özpek & Yaşar, 2018). Crisis – economic sabotage, Western plots, internal enemies – became permanent, allowing Erdoğan to govern through polarization, and the assertion that he alone embodies the general will.

In this sense, resentment, Islamism, nostalgia, and neo-Ottomanism are not merely aspects of Erdoğan's rhetoric.

They structure the emotional and moral logic of his authoritarian turn, transforming long-standing grievances into a durable mode of governance grounded in moralized victimhood, civilizational struggle, and personalized sovereignty. This political and institutional transformation was inseparable from Erdoğan's performative and psychological strategy. His rhetoric and public persona translate collective grievances into emotionally charged mobilization, blending ordinariness with extraordinariness to embody the people's aspirations and moral vindication. Drawing on the psychology of social emotions (Salmela & Capelos, 2021; Schori-Eyal & Halperin, 2020), Erdoğan channels shared experiences of humiliation and marginalization into moralized anger and pride. Through performative acts, such as visiting poor neighborhoods, adopting familiar speech, or emphasizing personal martyrdom, he signals proximity and authenticity, while simultaneously projecting exceptional qualities and divine favour. By weaving historical narratives of Ottoman grandeur with perceived contemporary injustices, Erdoğan enables what Branscombe et al. (1999) call *collective identity repair*, allowing supporters to reinterpret past suffering as proof of moral superiority. In this way, his populism is not only a set of ideological claims but also a deeply affective and therapeutic mechanism, giving emotional coherence and political energy to a constituency long burdened by social and cultural exclusion.

Erdoğan's populist narrative constructs a dichotomy between "the people" and "the elites," reframing political competition as a moral struggle. In this sense, the AKP's neo-Ottomanism operates as an *emotional regime* rooted in *ressentiment*, a mix of envy, moral anger, and nostalgia (Nietzsche, 1872/1967; Scheler, 1915/2010). Psychological theories of *intergroup emotions* help explain why this framing resonates: By defining a collective self-threatened by external and internal "others," Erdoğan cultivates a sense of *collective efficacy* and *moral entitlement* among his followers (Lickel et al., 2006). His invocations of Ottoman heritage, reminding his followers of the 'conquest of Istanbul' on every occasion, reconverting Hagia Sophia into a mosque (Tokdoğan, 2024), erecting monumental mosques like that on Çamlıca Hill, or building the Panorama 1453 Museum (Bozoğlu, 2019), serve as symbolic acts of emotional restitution, aimed at transforming the past, heritage, and sometimes humiliation, into collective pride.

These practices represent more than nationalist spectacle; they perform *collective emotional regulation*. By externalizing blame toward secular elites or Western actors, Erdoğan channels diffuse feelings of anger and anxiety into narratives of redemption and superiority. This process mirrors what Salmela and Capelos (2021) describe as the *transformation of resentment into identity maintenance*, whereby persistent grievances are reinterpreted as signs of moral

virtue. Erdoğan's supporters thus experience belonging not despite their perceived suffering, but *because of it*.

Finally, institutional mechanisms such as AKIM (AKP Communication Centre), BIMER (Prime Ministry Communication Centre, served between 2006 and 2018), and CIMER (Presidency Communication Centre) further consolidate this affective bond by simulating direct, emotional proximity between the leader and "the people", advanced under the rhetoric of "you govern" (Boyras, 2018). These populist communication channels reinforce the illusion of inclusion and empowerment – hallmarks of what psychological literature defines as *collective coping* in the face of perceived threat (Branscombe et al., 1999; Schori-Eyal & Halperin, 2020).

Erdoğan's rise exemplifies how *ressentiment* functions as an *emotional mechanism* of populist politics: converting collective humiliation into moralized pride, and transforming wounded identities into the psychological foundation of a populist project of national redemption. This emotional transformation does not remain confined to individual or partisan identification; it expands into a broader cultural and civilizational register. Through the articulation of neo-Ottomanism and Islamism, Erdoğan translates affective energies, particularly those of grievance, nostalgia, and pride, into a vision of counterhegemonic renewal. What begins as the emotional politics of *ressentiment* thus matures into a project of cultural reordering, seeking to redefine Turkey's collective memory and moral orientation against its secular and Westernized past.

Neo-Ottomanism and Islamism as a Countercultural Hegemony: *Ressentiment* Against the West

Erdoğan's populism translates the emotional energies of *ressentiment*, such as humiliation, nostalgia, and moral anger, into a civilizational project of cultural renewal. Nowhere is this clearer than in his 3 March 2017 address at Istanbul's third National Culture Forum, where he declared:

Culture is not just about books, music, or architecture, but is a lifestyle that includes all these things. From our greeting to the way we sit down and stand

up, what we wear, eat, drink, and the order of our house, we have many different elements shaping our culture. For the last few centuries, the world has been progressing rapidly on the path of cultural uniformity. This situation is a great threat not only to Turkish culture but also to all other cultures. Actually, we can turn this into an opportunity . . . Our generation, from idioms to some tools, is the last witness and user of a significant portion of our local culture. Newer generations are, unfortunately, left devoid of this richness and will continue to be so if things go on like this. *We will be left in the claws of a cultural drought if we cannot understand the culture of a person walking in the streets of Istanbul from his clothes, shoes, hat, and posture. Sitting at a dinner table, looking at the tablecloth and plates, the dishes and the way they are presented, if we cannot figure out which nation it belongs to, then the situation is really grave . . .* These debates are held in many parts of the world; the same pains appear everywhere. However, we have a difference. We are a very different nation in terms of civilizational and historical past, as well as in the state tradition. As the descendants of glorious ancestors who changed the age and ushered in a new era, we possess the power, the will, and the possibility to build a new and great future for ourselves. Here, we chant 'Great, powerful Turkey'. We want to achieve our 2023 goals. For this reason, we inherit the visions of 2053 and 2071 for our youth⁵ . . . We are struggling to introduce a new administrative system to our country through constitutional amendments. This is the reason why we place the native and the national at the centre of our policy, our point of departure. Within the framework of the 2023 vision, we have to set new cultural targets for ourselves. This is why the third National Cultural Council that we are attending today is of great importance in this respect (*italics are mine*).⁶

The speech exemplifies Erdoğan's long-standing ambition to establish a counterhegemonic cultural paradigm against Kemalist modernity. His nostalgic emphasis on Ottoman civilization, as a symbol of pluralism, multiculturalism, and moral order, serves both to reclaim a wounded collective memory and to moralize the political present. In psychological terms, this rhetoric channels *collective emotions*

⁵ See Erdoğan's Istanbul Airport Opening Speech, which attempts to mobilize his constituents for the 600th anniversary (in 2053) of the fall of Istanbul to the Ottoman Turks in 1453; see <https://www.tccb.gov.tr/en/speeches-statements/558/99431/president-erdogan-s-message-on-29-october-republic-day>, accessed on 22 November 2025. In the same speech, Erdoğan evoked not only the 600th anniversary vision of 2053 but also the millennial target of 2071, conceived to commemorate the mythicized Turkish entry into Anatolia at the Battle of Manzikert in 1071. This strategy reflects what Friedman (1992) describes as *mythopractice*: the intentional construction and mobilization of national myths to galvanize the public and advance the narrative of a "New Turkey."

⁶ Erdoğan's Third National Culture Forum Speech (3 March 2017), see <https://basin.ktb.gov.tr/TR-175032/3-milli-kultur-surasi-basladi.html>, accessed on 22 November 2025.

(Schori-Eyal & Halperin, 2020) of loss and humiliation into a shared sense of moral pride and national purpose (Branscombe et al., 1999).

Followers of Erdoğan often experience what Lickel et al. (2006) describe as vicarious shame and pride, emotions derived from identification with one's group and its historical trajectory. Erdoğan's speeches mobilize these emotions to create what Salmela and Capelos (2021) call an "affective community": a political collective bound not by ideology but by shared emotional narratives of victimhood and redemption. His Ottoman nostalgia – evoking "the culture of a person walking in the streets of Istanbul from his clothes, shoes, hat, and posture" – is less about heritage than about affective reparation: transforming historical wounds into a moral mission of national restoration.

By idealizing the Ottoman *millet* system as a model of harmony and civilizational grandeur, Erdoğan symbolically reverses the Kemalist rupture that defined modern Turkey's "civilized" identity through Westernization and secularism. In doing so, he reframes the humiliation of being excluded from the Western modernity project as a source of renewed dignity. This emotional inversion is central to the mechanism of *ressentiment*, which, as Nietzsche originally described and later political psychologists confirmed, reconstitutes weakness and wound into moral superiority and collective entitlement.

Such affective reworking occurs within a global context that elevates civilizational identity politics (Brubaker, 2017). Erdoğan's invocation of *yerli ve milli* ("native and national") functions not only as a political slogan but as an emotional code, an assertion of belonging that contrasts authentic Turkish-Muslim values against the moral emptiness of the secular, Westernized elite. Domestically, this binary resonates deeply: Erdoğan positions himself as the protector of authentic national identity, while casting his opponents, critical media, and secular intellectuals as betrayers of the nation's "true" self (Çağaptay, 2017).

Modernization in Turkey has long been equated with Europeanization, Westernization, and secularization, imagined as linear progress from tradition to modernity. The Kemalist reforms from the Romanized alphabet to the secular state signified both material and emotional separation from the Ottoman-Islamic past. As Bozdağlıoğlu (2008) argues, this historical process produced an enduring hierarchy of civilizations, wherein the West represented superiority and the East backwardness. Erdoğan's rhetoric subverts this hierarchy through emotional inversion: the formerly humiliated East becomes the moral and spiritual center, while the West is refigured as decadent and alienated. This civilizational reframing was made explicit in Erdoğan's

2012 speech at the Turkish-Arab Tourism Summit in Bursa, where he declared:

Although Turkey has turned in a direction towards the West, it will never turn its back on the East and South ... We cannot accept separation through artificial barriers from our friends, neighbours, relatives, or even brothers, with whom we have lived together for centuries.⁷

This statement articulates a dual emotional geography: resentment toward Western condescension combined with nostalgic attachment to the Islamic East. Erdoğan's foreign policy, therefore, draws upon collective memory and emotion, seeking both symbolic revenge and moral leadership in a global order perceived as unjust. Erdoğan's regional influence increasingly rests on a combination of economic and cultural engagement, the promotion of the "Turkish Model" of governance, and global advocacy rooted in identity politics. Turkey positions itself as a defender of disenfranchised populations, championing Palestine, opposing Islamophobia and neo-colonialism, and asserting a moral claim within a multipolar global order (Adar, 2024). This reflects how *ressentiment* and nostalgia combine to create a psychologically potent affective framework with an emphasis on the narrative of civilizational redemption, in which historical wounds are transformed into moral pride, collective purpose, and justification for both domestic and regional authority.

This affective framing intensified after the 2013 Gezi protests and the 15 July 2016 coup attempt, which heightened collective anxiety and moral indignation. The AKP used these crises to justify securitization, suppress dissent, and consolidate authoritarian rule, casting opponents as existential threats to an Islamic-Ottoman civilizational mission (Akdeniz & Altıparmak, 2018). Erdoğan's discourse converts grievance into political capital by linking loyalty to the defense of religious and historical values. Drawing on collective victimhood (Branscombe et al., 1999) and vicarious pride (Lickel et al., 2006), his neo-Ottomanism transforms resentment into a narrative of moral superiority and civilizational revival.

Erdoğan's Civilizational Rhetoric

From a psychological perspective, Erdoğan's neo-Ottomanism exemplifies the mobilization of collective victimhood (Branscombe et al., 1999) and vicarious pride (Lickel et al., 2006) within an affective community (Salmela &

⁷ Erdoğan, Recep Tayyip, Sırtımızı Doğu'ya, Güney'e dönmeyiz, in: *Dünya*, <https://www.dunya.com/gundem/sirtimizi-dogu039ya-guney039e-donmeyiz-haberi-172151>, accessed on 27 November 2025.

Capelos, 2021). By linking historical grievance, moral emotion, and identity processes, he transforms *ressentiment* into a driver of national revival and populist loyalty. Nostalgia for the Ottoman past, coupled with resentment toward perceived Kemalist and Western oppression, enables followers to internalize a narrative of moral superiority and historical rectitude. Erdoğan's civilizational rhetoric explicitly illustrates this emotional mobilization. In his 3 March 2017 speech at the third National Culture Forum, he articulates how cultural hegemony can be reconstructed against the Kemalist regime, which he frames as alienated from authentic Ottoman-Islamic values:

If you don't look at Istanbul from Fatih's eyes [Mehmet II, the Conqueror of Constantinople], you'll see a city that is just a mixture of stone and concrete and sea. If you do not look at Bursa from the eyes of Orhan Gazi [an early Ottoman Sultan] and Edirne from the eyes of Sultan Murat, you will not know the secrets of these cities and the civilization they represent. Once you do not look at our waving flag with the eyes of our martyrs, veterans, that colour, that crescent, that star cannot say anything beyond being a graphic. However, what does Arif Nihat Asya say? "O white and red ornament of blue skies, / My sister's wedding dress, the last cloth of my martyr, / My bright and waving flag! / I have read your epic, I will write your epic." Yes, what we need is a consciousness of national culture to see our flag like this. Remember, you can rule by elections, votes, and polls, but cultural hegemony needs labour, hard work, and sweat. We must rediscover and reconstruct our cultural values with a universalist perspective against cultural alienation and imperialism. The fact that the form of a cultural product is indigenous and national does not preclude the universalization of its meaning and message.⁸

By invoking Ottoman sultans alongside a nationalist-conservative poet, Arif Nihat Asya, Erdoğan encourages an affective identification with an Islamic-Ottoman civilizational lineage. Followers are called to internalize a sense of moralized pride and historical continuity, aligning with psychological theories that link collective memory to present-day emotional and social identification (Salmela & Capelos, 2021; Schori-Eyal & Halperin, 2020). This nostalgic framing resonates deeply among constituencies that perceive themselves as historically marginalized and morally wronged, reinforcing *ressentiment* as an enduring

affective mechanism. Erdoğan further clarifies the ontological meaning of civilization in a speech at Ibn Haldun University, Istanbul, on 21 October 2017:

The essence of civilization is faith, and religion constitutes an umbrella over civilization. The prophet Mohammad created the pillars of Islamic civilization, and its roots are laid in the Quran ... Civilization is not only composed of science and technique; faith and social solidarity are even more important constituents. In this respect, the style and dimensions of Western civilization and Islamic civilization are different. For example, for a city to be considered civilized according to Western civilization, there should be city lights on roads, no mud on the streets, whereas according to Islamic civilization, the main indicators of a civilized city is to be able to go out without locking the door, to extend the hand to everyone in need, and even to care tenderly for street animals. This is what we call civilization. Having 40-storey buildings or 100-storey buildings does not make you civilized. Unfortunately, we have also fallen into this trap.⁹

This definition radically departs from Kemalist conceptions of Western-oriented civilization, which prioritize material development, science, and urbanization (Berkes, 1959; Gökalp, 1976). Whereas the Kemalist framework sought to harmonize Turkish identity with European material progress, summarized in Gökalp's motto, "We belong to the Turkish nation, the Muslim religious community and the European civilization" (Gökalp, 1976), Erdoğan's model places Islamic faith at the core, subordinating material and ethnic markers to a civilizational-religious ethos. In reinforcing this narrative, Erdoğan urges cultural action, framing it as essential to national survival:

My expectation from you is as follows: Prepare for us a practical roadmap with depth and a vision of the future. You need to work on this very well. Let's work it out and put it into practice. I would like to say that I will be a follower of every reasonable and feasible proposal that will be put forth here. I will form a delegation to this end. It is for this purpose that we are gathered here today for the National Culture Forum. Let's not forget that if we forget our civilization, we lose everything. If we lose our culture, we disappear. If we leave our identity, our personality, our authenticity, we will be lost in the masses. On every occasion, we are chanting 'One nation, one flag, one homeland,

⁸ Erdoğan's Third National Culture Forum Speech (3 March 2017), <https://basin.ktb.gov.tr/TR-175032/3-milli-kultur-surasi-basladi.html>

⁹ For Erdoğan's Civilizational Forum Speech (21 October 2017), see <https://www.fikriyat.com/kultur-sanat/2017/10/21/medeniyetler-surasi-basladi>, accessed on 22 November 2025.

one state'. These principles constitute the security valve of our independence and our future. To be able to look confidently to our future, not to be dispersed into fragmentation, and in the face of those who want to divide us, we need to be much more alive, intact, and strong as brothers. We will all be one Turkey. To address this goal, we must protect our national culture. As the deceased Cemil Meriç once said, when we are stormed, we should take care of our books, our culture and our civilization. As we move away from our culture, we know that we will alienate ourselves, and as we become alien to ourselves, we will enter the yoke of those who are stronger.¹⁰

Here, Erdoğan links identity, culture, and political resilience, portraying cultural preservation as a moral and civilizational imperative. From a social-psychological perspective, this rhetoric transforms collective grievances into a unifying emotional project, in which the affective experience of victimhood is redirected into moralized pride and national purpose (Branscombe et al., 1999; Lickel et al., 2006). It also reinforces a binary worldview: those aligned with Islamic-Ottoman values versus those representing Kemalist or Western alienation, echoing Scheler's and Nietzsche's conceptualizations of *ressentiment* as a moralized response to perceived historical and structural injustice (Nietzsche, 1872; Scheler, 1915/2010).

Through these speeches, Erdoğan demonstrates the psychological mechanisms by which populist leaders harness historical grievance. The repeated linking of Ottoman symbols, Islamic faith, and national pride fosters an affective community in which followers experience both vicarious pride and collective victimhood. *Ressentiment* becomes not only a vehicle for political loyalty but also a moral and emotional framework for interpreting Turkey's present and envisioning its future, turning past humiliation into a resource for contemporary mobilization (Salmela & Capeos, 2021; Schori-Eyal & Halperin, 2020).

Conclusion

This article has shown that Erdoğan's neo-Ottomanist project is not only political and ideological but profoundly populist and psychological. It relies on social emotions – particularly *ressentiment*, collective victimhood, and moralized pride – to shape collective identity and mobilize political behavior. Historically embedded feelings of humiliation, exclusion, and injustice constitute a durable affective framework that Erdoğan leverages to sustain loyalty,

legitimize authority, and animate his populist agenda. By linking historical pride with narratives of victimization, he transforms wounded identities into political energy, using rhetoric, symbolic acts, and performative leadership – from Ottoman grandeur to martyrdom – to reinforce group boundaries, collective memory, and moralized threat.

The fusion of nostalgia and *ressentiment* provides followers with pride, belonging, and a moral framework while directing anger and vigilance toward internal and external adversaries. This affective strategy strengthens cohesion, justifies authoritarian measures, and sustains a vision of national and civilizational resurgence, even amid crises. Erdoğan's populism exemplifies how historical grievances and social emotions can be harnessed to convert collective *ressentiment* into moral triumph, shared purpose, and enduring political allegiance, demonstrating the centrality of affective regimes in contemporary populist governance.

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¹⁰ Erdoğan's Third National Culture Forum Speech (3 March 2017), <https://basin.ktb.gov.tr/TR-175032/3-milli-kultur-surasi-basladi.html>, accessed on 22 November 2025.

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